

This is a peer-reviewed, post-print (final draft post-refereeing) version. The final publication is available at <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40279-019-01211-9>

Raya-González, J., Rendo-Urteaga, T., Domínguez, R., Castillo, D., Rodríguez-Fernández, A., & Grgic, J. (2020). Acute Effects of Caffeine Supplementation on Movement Velocity in Resistance Exercise: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Sports Medicine*, 50(4), 717–729. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-019-01211-9>

Official URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40279-019-01211-9>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-019-01211-9>

PMID: 31643020

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Abstract

Background: Several studies have investigated the effects of caffeine supplementation on movement velocity in resistance exercise. However, the findings across these studies are equivocal.

Objective: This paper aimed to: (a) review the studies that explored the effects of caffeine supplementation on movement velocity in resistance exercise; and (b) pool their results using a meta-analysis.

Methods: A search for studies was performed through five databases. Random-effects meta-analyses of standardized mean differences (SMD) were performed to analyze the data. Subgroup meta-analyses explored the effects of caffeine on different velocity variables (i.e., mean vs. peak velocity), different loads (i.e., low, moderate, and high loads), and upper and lower-body exercises.

Results: A total of ten studies met the inclusion criteria. In the main meta-analysis, in which we pooled all available studies, the SMD favored the caffeine condition (SMD = 0.85; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.33–1.36; $p < 0.001$). Subgroup analyses indicated that caffeine significantly enhances mean (SMD = 1.06; 95% CI: 0.14–1.97; $p = 0.024$) and peak velocity (SMD = 0.57; 95% CI: 0.27–0.86; $p < 0.001$), velocity with moderate loads (SMD = 1.48; 95% CI: 0.52–2.44; $p = 0.003$), and high loads (SMD = 2.02; 95% CI: 0.82–3.22; $p = 0.001$), as well as in lower-body (SMD = 1.23; 95% CI: 0.15–2.30; $p = 0.026$) and upper-body exercises (SMD = 0.94; 95% CI: 0.33–1.55; $p = 0.003$). We did not find a significant effect of caffeine on movement velocity when exercising with low loads (SMD = 0.79; 95% CI: -0.01 to 1.59; $p = 0.053$).

Conclusion: Based on the results of this review, acute caffeine supplementation is highly ergogenic for movement velocity in resistance exercise. Subgroup analyses indicated that caffeine ingestion is ergogenic: (a) for both mean and peak velocity; (b) when exercising with moderate and high loads, and (c) in both lower and upper-body exercises. Previous meta-analyses that explored the effects of caffeine on various aspects of exercise performance reported trivial to moderate ergogenic effects (effect size range: 0.16–0.51). In the present meta-analysis, the pooled effect size magnitude ranged from 0.57 to 2.02. From an exercise performance standpoint, this suggests that caffeine has the most pronounced performance-enhancing effects on movement velocity.

Key points

- a) Acute caffeine supplementation seems to be highly ergogenic for movement velocity in resistance exercise.
- b) The ergogenic effects of caffeine were noted for both mean and peak velocity and were significant across moderate and high loads and in both lower and upper-body exercises.

1 Introduction

The 2018 International Olympic Committee consensus statement classified caffeine as a nutritional supplement that has good evidence of benefits for enhancing exercise performance [1]. As such, caffeine is widely consumed by athletes. Studies that examined the prevalence of caffeine ingestion among different groups of athletes reported that those competing in strength and power-based sports are among the highest users of caffeine, in terms of frequency [2].

Many primary studies and several meta-analyses have explored the effects of caffeine on muscle strength [3–8]. The currently published meta-analyses investigated the effects of caffeine on one-repetition maximum (1RM), isokinetic, and isometric strength [3, 7, 8]. These meta-analyses [7, 8, 3] reported ergogenic effects of caffeine on strength in the effect size magnitude of 0.16 for isokinetic strength (95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.06 to 0.26), 0.19 for isometric strength (95% CI: 0.09, 0.29), and 0.20 for 1RM strength (95% CI: 0.03, 0.36), respectively. These effects are considered to be of small or trivial magnitudes.

A recent review posited that caffeine's effects might be greater on movement velocity (i.e., a form of power expression) than on maximal muscle strength [4]. In resistance exercise, movement velocity is often assessed by using tools that measure barbell speed (such as linear position transducers). These tools can provide a full load-velocity profile (i.e., performance at different percentages of the 1RM) which may be relevant when it comes to caffeine supplementation given that the effects of caffeine might not be uniform across different external loads [4]. Furthermore, this is important if we consider that resistance training is commonly performed with sub-maximal loads, whereas maximal strength expression in the practical context is not as frequent. Finally, velocity based measures provide both mean velocity (the average velocity from the start of the concentric phase until the bar reaches the maximum height) and peak velocity data (maximum velocity reached during the concentric phase) and both variables are relevant to athletes [9].

Several recent studies have investigated the effects of caffeine supplementation on movement velocity in resistance exercise [10–19]. However, the findings across these studies have been equivocal [10–19]. Therefore, this paper aimed to: (a) review the studies that explored the effects of caffeine supplementation on movement velocity in resistance exercise; (b) pool their results using a meta-analysis; and (c) provide additional context to this topic by focusing on potential moderating study characteristics such as the effects of caffeine on different velocity

variables (i.e., mean and peak velocity), the effects of caffeine on movement velocity with different external loads, and the effects of caffeine in upper vs. lower-body exercises.

2 Methods

The present review was carried out following the recommendations and criteria established in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) statement guidelines [20].

2.1 Search strategy

For this systematic review, searches were performed through PubMed/MEDLINE, SPORTDiscus, Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations, ProQuest Dissertation & Theses, and Open Access Theses and Dissertations databases. The search syntax included the following keywords coupled with Boolean operators: "caffeine" AND ("mean velocity" OR "peak velocity" OR "resistance exercise" OR "resistance training" OR "strength exercise" OR "strength training" OR "bench press" OR "speed" OR "mean power" OR "peak power" OR "squat" OR "leg press" OR "leg extension" OR "ballistic"). Secondary searches included: (a) screening the reference lists of all included studies and relevant review papers [3, 4, 7, 8]; (b) examining the studies that cited the included studies (i.e., forward citation tracking) through Google Scholar; and (c) conducting additional searches through ResearchGate. Two authors (JRG and RD) independently performed the searches; any discrepancies between the authors in the study selection were resolved in consultation with a third reviewer (DC). The search was performed on April 9th, 2019, with no date restriction.

2.2 Inclusion criteria

Studies meeting the following criteria were included: (a) an experimental trial published in English; (b) included humans without chronic disease or injury as study participants; (c) utilized a single or double-blind crossover design with at least one placebo and one caffeine trial; and (d) assessed the effects of caffeine ingestion in any form (as long as the effects of caffeine could be isolated) on movement velocity during resistance exercise. When required, corresponding authors from the included studies were contacted to provide the required data or to clarify certain aspects of the study design. To avoid possible publication bias, we included studies published in peer-reviewed journals as well as theses, dissertations, and conference abstracts.

2.3 Study coding and data extraction

The following data were extracted from the included studies: (a) study design; (b) sample characteristics (including age, sex, sample size, and training status); (c) dose, form, and timing of caffeine ingestion; (d) exercises, loads, and velocity variables used for the testing; (e) main findings from the caffeine and placebo conditions. Data extraction was performed independently by two authors (JRG and DC).

2.4 Methodological quality

The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using the Physiotherapy Evidence Database Scale (PEDro) [21, 22]. The full details regarding the PEDro scale can be found elsewhere [22]. The PEDro scale has 11 items. However, the maximal score on the scale is 10, as the first item concerns external validity, and it is not included in the total score. Each question is answered with “yes” if the criteria are satisfied or with a “no” if the criteria are not satisfied; here, only the answer “yes” corresponds to one point. Based on the summary score, the methodological quality of the included was categorized as follows: excellent quality (9 to 10 points), good quality (6 to 8 points), fair quality (4 to 5 points), or poor quality (<3 points) [3, 7, 23]. The methodological quality appraisal was independently performed by two authors (JRG and ARF); discrepancies between the authors were resolved in consultation with a third reviewer (DC).

2.5 Statistical analyses

A random-effects meta-analysis was performed using the statistical software STATA 14 (Stata Corp., College Station, TX, USA). Standardized mean differences (Hedge’s g [SMD]) and 95% CIs were calculated between the placebo and caffeine trials based on the exercise performance mean and standard deviation data from the placebo and caffeine conditions, the correlation between the trials, and the number of participants. Given that none of the included studies reported correlation values, a conservative 0.5 correlation was assumed for all studies [24]. The SMD magnitude was interpreted as: (a) trivial (<0.20); (b) small (0.20 to 0.49); (c) moderate (0.50 to 0.79); and (d) large (≥ 0.80) [25]. The statistical significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$.

In the main analysis, we pooled all available data. This included combining mean and peak velocity data, values obtained with different external loads, as well as values obtained using both upper and lower-body exercises. In this analysis, when a study measured movement

velocity under multiple conditions, such as multiple loads, SMDs and variances were calculated for each outcome separately, and average SMD and variance values were used for the analysis. Sub-group analyses explored the effects of caffeine on different velocity variables (i.e., mean and peak velocity), different loads (i.e., low, moderate, and high), and upper and lower-body exercises. In the sub-group analysis for different loads, low load was considered as <30% 1RM, moderate load was between 30% and 70% 1RM, and high load was from 70% to 100% 1RM. Heterogeneity was measured using the I^2 statistic. I^2 values lower than 50% indicated low heterogeneity, I^2 values from 50% to 75% indicated moderate heterogeneity and I^2 values >75% indicated a high level of heterogeneity.

We also calculated 95% prediction intervals (95% PI) for each analysis by using the number of included studies, the pooled standardized mean difference (SMD), the upper limit of the 95% CI, and the tau-squared values. The 95% PI represents the range in which the SMD of a future study conducted on the topic will most likely be.

3 Results

3.1 Search results

The total number of search results was 607. A total of 584 search results were excluded based on their titles and/or abstracts; therefore, 23 full-text articles were read. Sixteen articles were excluded from the review because they did not examine the effects of caffeine on movement velocity or because they presented duplicate data. Seven studies were initially included; however, three additional studies were found through the secondary searches, and therefore, a total of ten studies were included in the review [10–19; Figure 1].

3.2 Descriptive characteristics of the studies

The included studies are summarized in Table 1. The studies were published between 2012 and 2019, and all used a randomized double-blind design. The total sample size across all studies was 154 participants. Eight studies included only males, and two included both males and females. All studies were conducted in young adults. In seven of the studies, the participants were classified as athletes or highly resistance-trained while in the remaining three, the participants were considered as recreationally active. For the studies that provided caffeine doses per kilogram of body weight, the doses ranged from 1 to 9 mg·kg⁻¹. For the studies that provided absolute doses, the caffeine dose ranged from 158 to 328 mg.

3.3 Meta-analysis results

In the main meta-analysis, the pooled effect favored the caffeine condition (SMD = 0.85; 95% CI: 0.33 to 1.36; 95% PI: -0.95 to 2.65; $p < 0.001$; $I^2 = 80.2\%$; [Figure 2]).

Subgroup meta-analysis indicated that caffeine significantly enhances mean movement velocity (SMD = 1.06; 95% CI: 0.14 to 1.97; 95% PI: -2.20 to 4.32; $p = 0.024$; $I^2 = 89.0\%$; [Figure 3A]) and peak movement velocity (SMD = 0.57; 95% CI: 0.27 to 0.86; 95% PI: 0.10 to 1.04; $p < 0.001$; $I^2 = 0.0\%$; [Figure 3B]).

Subgroup meta-analysis indicated that caffeine significantly improves movement velocity with moderate loads (SMD = 1.48; 95% CI: 0.52 to 2.44; 95% PI: -1.90 to 4.85; $p = 0.003$; $I^2 = 89.6\%$; [Figure 4B]), and high loads (SMD = 2.02; 95% CI: 0.82 to 3.22; 95% PI: -2.27 to 6.31; $p = 0.001$; $I^2 = 91.9\%$; [Figure 4C]). No significant effects were found with low loads (SMD = 0.79; 95% CI: -0.01 to 1.59; 95% PI: -2.16 to 3.74; $p = 0.053$; $I^2 = 83.2\%$; [Figure 4A]).

Subgroup meta-analysis indicated that caffeine significantly improves movement velocity in lower-body exercises (SMD = 1.23; 95% CI: 0.15 to 2.30; 95% PI: -2.83 to 5.29; $p = 0.026$; $I^2 = 88.2\%$; [Figure 5A]) and upper-body exercises (SMD = 0.94; 95% CI: 0.33 to 1.55; 95% PI: -1.20 to 3.08; $p = 0.003$; $I^2 = 84.4\%$; [Figure 5B]).

3.4 Methodological quality

The average score on the PEDro scale was 9.5 ± 1 , with the values from individual studies ranging from 8 to 10. Eight studies were categorized as being of excellent methodological quality, and two studies were categorized as being of good quality. Individual scores for the quality assessment can be found in Table 2.

4 Discussion

The main finding of this review is that caffeine may be ergogenic for movement velocity in resistance exercise. These ergogenic effects were found for both mean and peak velocity. Additionally, performance-enhancing effects of caffeine were found when exercising with moderate and high loads, and in both upper as well as lower-body exercises. All included studies had a double-blind design and were categorized as being of good or excellent methodological quality, which therefore strengthens these conclusions.

A recent umbrella review summarized all meta-analyses that explored the effects of caffeine ingestion on exercise performance [26]. This umbrella review found that caffeine is ergogenic for several aspects of exercise performance, including aerobic endurance, muscle strength, muscle endurance, power output during Wingate tests, jumping performance, and exercise speed. The pooled effect sizes across the meta-analyses ranged from 0.16 to 0.51. These effects were classified as being of trivial to moderate magnitudes. In the present meta-analysis, the effect sizes were greater as they ranged from 0.57 to 2.02 and are considered as being of large magnitudes. Based on this comparison of effect sizes between meta-analyses, from an exercise performance standpoint, it seems that caffeine has the most pronounced ergogenic effects on movement velocity. This notion also has a substantial physiological support given that caffeine may: (a) increase motor unit recruitment, muscle fiber conduction velocity, and voluntary activation [27]; (b) increase the rate of calcium release from the sarcoplasmic reticulum [28]; and (c) may have a direct effect on the skeletal muscle tissue [29]. All these physiological responses to caffeine ingestion may result in a more forceful muscular contraction and make caffeine very conducive for increasing movement velocity.

An interesting finding of this review is that caffeine's effects seem to be higher for mean as compared to peak velocity (SMD of 1.07 and 0.57, respectively). Most of the studies included in this analysis measured either mean or peak velocity. In other words, there is a lack of studies exploring the effects of caffeine on both velocity variables in the same groups of participants. This aspect is important to emphasize given the considerable inter-individual variation in responses to caffeine ingestion as it pertains to its effects on exercise performance [30]. Therefore, future studies on this topic may consider measuring both mean and peak velocity in the same sample to explore if the magnitude of caffeine's effects indeed differs between these two velocity variables.

The use of velocity-based measures in resistance exercise allows the assessment of a full load-velocity profile. This is important to establish given that moderate loads (from 30% to 70% 1RM) seem to provide the optimal load for power development (even though this may be exercise dependent) [31]. The results obtained in the present review indicate that SMDs for the effects of caffeine on movement velocity increase with the external load. The pooled SMD for low loads amounted to 0.79 (95% CI: -0.01 to 1.59), rose to 1.48 (95% CI: 0.52 to 2.44) for moderate loads, and was the highest for high loads (SMD: 2.02; 95% CI: 0.82 to 3.22). These

results may tentatively suggest that the effects of caffeine are the greatest when the force production requirements are the highest. With that being said, the 95% CIs were relatively wide, and they largely overlapped between the analyses for different loads; therefore, the findings need to be interpreted with a dose of caution. Future studies on this topic are needed given that each of these analyses included a total of six studies and there was a high degree of heterogeneity in each meta-analysis (I^2 ranged from 83.2% to 91.9%).

Previous meta-analyses have observed that the effects of caffeine on strength are not uniform between the upper and lower-body musculature [7, 8]. In the meta-analysis by Warren et al. [8], a significant effect of caffeine on isometric strength was found in the lower but not upper-body musculature. In contrast to these findings, Grgic et al. [3] reported that caffeine ingestion enhances 1RM strength in the upper but not lower-body musculature. However, our results suggest that caffeine may be similarly effective for both upper-body (SMD: 0.94; 95% CI: 0.33 to 1.55) and lower-body musculature (SMD: 1.23; 95% CI: 0.15 to 2.30). These results are different from previous meta-analyses likely because the physiological mechanism(s) that underpin caffeine's ergogenic effects on strength are different from those that are responsible for the performance-enhancing effects on contraction velocity. Future studies are warranted to explore the reasons for these divergent findings.

4.1 Methodological quality

As assessed using the PEDro checklist, the included studies are classified as being of good or excellent methodological quality. However, we noted one methodological limitation specific to studies focusing on sports supplements in the vast majority of the included studies. Out of the ten included studies, only Venier et al. [19] explored the effectiveness of the blinding of participants to the caffeine and placebo conditions. In this study, when examined pre-exercise, a total of 78% and 32% of participants correctly identified the placebo and caffeine conditions beyond random chance, respectively. Post-exercise, for the placebo and caffeine conditions, these values amounted to 63% and 53%, respectively. This aspect regarding blinding is relevant to highlight given the recent findings that correct supplement identification may influence an outcome of a given exercise task and therefore, present a source of bias in the sports nutrition line of research [32]. This methodological aspect should be adequately explored and addressed in future studies to increase the robustness of the presented findings.

4.2 Limitations

There are several limitations of this review that need to be acknowledged. One such limitation is that there were not enough studies to allow meta-regression analysis that would help to determine the 'optimal' dose of caffeine for enhancing movement velocity in resistance exercise. Additionally, the number of female participants was small (Table 1), which limits the generalizability of these findings to women. With that being said, one study included both men and women and reported similar ergogenic effects of caffeine in both sexes [16]; however, future studies conducted in women are needed to confirm these findings.

5 Conclusion

Based on the results of this review, acute caffeine supplementation seems to be highly ergogenic for movement velocity in resistance exercise. Sub-group analyses indicated that caffeine ingestion is ergogenic for both mean and peak velocity. The effects of caffeine on movement velocity were significant when exercising with moderate and high loads and in both lower as well as upper-body exercises. Therefore, individuals interested in the acute enhancement of movement velocity in resistance exercise may consider supplementing with caffeine pre-exercise.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Funding

No sources of funding were used for this work.

Conflict of interest

Javier Raya-González, Tara Rendo-Urteaga, Raúl Domínguez, Daniel Castillo, Alejandro Rodríguez-Fernández and Jozo Grgic declare that they have no conflicts of interest relevant to the content of this review.

References

1. Maughan RJ, Burke LM, Dvorak J, Larson-Meyer DE, Peeling P, Phillips SM, et al. IOC Consensus Statement: Dietary supplements and the high-performance athlete. *Int J Sport Nutr Exerc Metab.* 2018;28(2):104–25.
2. Van Thuyne W, Delbeke F. Distribution of caffeine levels in urine in different sports in relation to doping control before and after the removal of caffeine from the WADA doping list. *Int J Sports Med.* 2006;27(9):745–50.
3. Grgic J, Trexler ET, Lazinica B, Pedisic Z. Effects of caffeine intake on muscle strength and power: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2018;15(1):11.
4. Grgic J, Mikulic P, Schoenfeld BJ, Bishop DJ, Pedisic Z. The influence of caffeine supplementation on resistance exercise: A review. *Sports Med.* 2019;49(1):17–30.
5. Grgic J, Mikulic P. Caffeine ingestion acutely enhances muscular strength and power but not muscular endurance in resistance-trained men. *Eur J Sport Sci.* 2017;17(8):1029–36.
6. Goldstein E, Jacobs PL, Whitehurst M, Penhollow T, Antonio J. Caffeine enhances upper body strength in resistance-trained women. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2010;7:18.
7. Grgic J, Pickering C. The effects of caffeine ingestion on isokinetic muscular strength: A meta-analysis. *J Sci Med Sport.* 2019;22(3):353–60.
8. Warren GL, Park ND, Maresca RD, McKibans KiI, Millard-Stafford ML. Effect of caffeine ingestion on muscular strength and endurance: a meta-analysis. *Med Sci Sport Exerc.* 2010;42(7):1375–87.
9. García-Ramos A, Pestaña-Melero FL, Pérez-Castilla A, Rojas FJ, Gregory Haff G. Mean velocity vs. mean propulsive velocity vs. peak velocity. *J Strength Cond Res.* 2018;32(5):1273–9.
10. Del Coso J, Salinero JJ, Gonzalez-Millan C, Abian-Vicen J, Perez-Gonzalez B. Dose response effects of a caffeine-containing energy drink on muscle performance: A repeated measures design. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2012;9(1):21.
11. Pallarés JG, Fernández-Elías VE, Ortega JF, Muñoz G, Muñoz-Guerra J, Mora-Rodríguez R. Neuromuscular responses to incremental caffeine doses: Performance and side effects. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2013;45(11):2184–92.
12. Mora-Rodríguez R, Pallarés JG, López-Gullón JM, López-Samanes Á, Fernández-Elías VE, Ortega JF. Improvements on neuromuscular performance with caffeine ingestion depend on the time-of-day. *J Sci Med Sport.* 2015;18(3):338–42.

13. Mora-Rodriguez R, Garcia Pallares J, Lopez-Samanes A, Ortega JF, Fernandez-Elias VE. Caffeine ingestion reverses the circadian rhythm effects on neuromuscular performance in highly resistance-trained men. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(4):e33807.
14. Kammerer E, Krings T, Wojton S, Scheckel E, Kuklinski E, Jacobs K, et al. The effects of a caffeine-containing beverage on muscle explosiveness during ballistic bench throws. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr*. 2012;9(Suppl 1):P15.
15. Goggin C, Kirk S, Powers CM, Smith R, Slotta A, Betro A, et al. Effects of Via® instant coffee on explosive squat performance. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2013;63(Suppl 1):566.
16. Wise A, Frank M, Holy A, Mohny S, Lowery L. The effects of VIA® Instant Coffee on bench press performance: a gender comparison. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr*. 2014;11(Suppl 1):P13.
17. Diaz-Lara FJ, Del Coso J, García JM, Portillo LJ, Areces F, Abián-Vicén J. Caffeine improves muscular performance in elite Brazilian Jiu-jitsu athletes. *Eur J Sport Sci*. 2016;16(8):1079–86.
18. Lane M, Byrd M, Lane MT, Byrd MT. Effects of pre-workout supplements on power maintenance in lower body and upper body tasks. *J Funct Morphol Kinesiol*. 2018;3(1):11.
19. Venier S, Grgic J, Mikulic P. Acute enhancement of jump performance, muscle strength, and power in resistance-trained men after consumption of caffeinated chewing gum. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform*. 2019. Doi: 10.1123/ijsp.2019-0098
20. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, PRISMA group. preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *PLoS Med*. 2009;6(7):e1000097.
21. de Morton NA. The PEDro scale is a valid measure of the methodological quality of clinical trials: a demographic study. *Aust J Physiother*. 2009;55(2):129–33.
22. Maher CG, Sherrington C, Herbert RD, Moseley AM, Elkins M. Reliability of the PEDro scale for rating quality of randomized controlled trials. *Phys Ther*. 2003;83(8):713–21.
23. McCrary JM, Ackermann BJ, Halaki M. A systematic review of the effects of upper body warm-up on performance and injury. *Br J Sports Med*. 2015;49(14):935–42.
24. Follmann D, Elliott P, Suh I, Cutler J. Variance imputation for overviews of clinical trials with continuous response. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 1992;45(7):769–73.
25. Cohen J. *Statistical Power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. Hillsdale, N.J: L. Erlbaum Associates.; 1988.

26. Grgic J, Grgic I, Pickering C, Schoenfeld BJ, Bishop DJ, Pedisic Z. Wake up and smell the coffee: caffeine supplementation and exercise performance-an umbrella review of 21 published meta-analyses. *Br J Sports Med.* 2019. Doi: 10.1136/bjsports-2018-100278
27. Bazzucchi I, Felici F, Montini M, Figura F, Sacchetti M. Caffeine improves neuromuscular function during maximal dynamic exercise. *Muscle Nerve.* 2011 Jun;43(6):839–44.
28. Tarnopolsky MA. Effect of caffeine on the neuromuscular system — potential as an ergogenic aid. *Appl Physiol Nutr Metab.* 2008;33(6):1284–9.
29. Tallis J, James RS, Cox VM, Duncan MJ. The effect of physiological concentrations of caffeine on the power output of maximally and submaximally stimulated mouse EDL (fast) and soleus (slow) muscle. *J Appl Physiol.* 2012;112(1):64–71.
30. Pickering C, Kiely J. Are the current guidelines on caffeine use in sport optimal for everyone? inter-individual variation in caffeine ergogenicity, and a move towards personalised sports nutrition. *Sports Med.* 2018;48(1):7–16.
31. Soriano MA, Jiménez-Reyes P, Rhea MR, Marín PJ. The optimal load for maximal power production during lower-body resistance exercises: A meta-analysis. *Sports Med.* 2015;45(8):1191–205.
32. Saunders B, de Oliveira LF, da Silva RP, de Salles Painelli V, Gonçalves LS, Yamaguchi G, et al. Placebo in sports nutrition: a proof-of-principle study involving caffeine supplementation. *Scand J Med Sci Sports.* 2017;27(11):1240–7.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the studies included in the meta-analysis

Study	Study design	Participants age (years) (mean \pm SD)	Sample size	Sex	Training status	Caffeine dose and form	Timing of caffeine ingestion	Velocity outcomes	Load	Resistance exercises
Mora-Rodríguez et al. (2012)	RDB	20 \pm 3	12	Men	Highly resistance-training	3 mg/kg in capsules	60 min pre-exercise	Mean velocity	Load that elicited a bar displacement of 1.00 m·s ⁻¹ and 75% 1RM	Full-squat and bench press
Kammerer et al. (2012)	RDB	NR	16	Men	Recreationally active	158 mg in an energy drink*	60 min pre-exercise	Peak velocity	50% RM	Ballistic bench throw
Del Coso et al. (2012)	RDB	30 \pm 7	9 men and 3 women	Both	Recreationally active	1 and 3 mg/kg in an energy drink**	60 min pre-exercise	Mean velocity	From 10 to 100% of 1RM (10% increments)	Half-squat and bench press
Goggin et al. (2013)	RDB	23 \pm 5	12	Men	Highly resistance-training	328 mg in VIA™ Ready Brew Coffee	60 min pre-exercise	Peak velocity	30% RM	Explosive squat
Pallarés et al. (2013)	RDB	22 \pm 3	13	Men	Highly resistance-training	3, 6, and 9 mg/kg in capsules	60 min pre-exercise	Mean velocity	25-50-75-90% 1RM	Full-squat and bench press
Wise et al. (2014)	RDB	21 \pm 4	12 men and 11 women	Both	Highly resistance-training	328 mg in VIA™ Ready Brew Coffee	60 min pre-exercise	Peak velocity	30% 1RM	Bench press
Mora-Rodríguez et al. (2015)	RDB	22 \pm 3	13	Men	Highly resistance-training	6 mg/kg in capsules	60 min pre-exercise	Mean velocity	25-50-75-90% 1RM	Full-squat and bench press

Díaz-Lara et al. (2016)	RDB	29 ± 3	14	Men	BJJ Athletes	3 mg/kg in capsules	60 min pre-exercise	Peak velocity	45% 1RM	Bench press
Lane et al. (2018)	RDB	23 ± 4	23	Men	Recreationally active	300 mg in liquid	25 min pre-exercise	Mean/peak velocity	80% 1RM	Bench press
Venier et al. (2019)	RDB	24 ± 5	19	Men	Highly resistance-training	300 mg in chewing gum	10 min pre-exercise	Mean velocity	50-75-90% 1RM	Bench press

Abbreviations: NR = not reported; RDB: randomized double-blind; BJJ: Brazilian jiu-jitsu; 1RM = one repetition maximum; * the only ergogenic compound in the energy drink was caffeine; ** the only difference between caffeine and placebo was the content of caffeine

Table 2. Results from the methodological quality assessment

Study/Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Score
Mora-Rodríguez et al. (2012)	Yes	Yes	10									
Kammerer et al. (2012)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	8						
Del Coso et al. (2012)	Yes	Yes	10									
Goggin et al. (2013)	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	9						
Pallarés et al. (2013)	Yes	Yes	10									
Wise et al. (2014)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	8						
Mora-Rodríguez et al. (2015)	Yes	Yes	10									
Díaz-Lara et al. (2016)	Yes	Yes	10									
Lane et al. (2018)	Yes	Yes	10									
Venier et al. (2019)	Yes	Yes	10									

Yes = criterion is satisfied; No = criterion is not satisfied.

